

Health Impact of Microplastics in the Blood and Health Risk Assessment of the Continuous Consumption of Plastics in Food

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Abstract: Microplastics are found nearly everywhere in packaging such as bowls, wraps, bottles, and bags used for food storage. As a result, people may unknowingly ingest small plastic fragments with regular meals. This study investigated the health impact of microplastics in the blood and health risk assessment of the continuous consumption of plastics in food. Two groups of six male and six female mice were used for the study. A group of three male and three female served as the treated group while the other group served as the control. The feed was amended with plastic powder. The mice were fed and observed for 28 days after which blood samples were collected from the mice to evaluate for the presence of plasticizers and measurement of haematological parameters. From the results, the treated group had the following values for red blood cell, hemoglobin and hematocrit $6.92 \pm 0.35 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$, $12.1 \pm 0.85\text{g/dL}$ and $38.2 \pm 2.1\%$ respectively while the control group had $7.85 \pm 0.22 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$, $14.2 \pm 0.6\text{g/dL}$ and $43.0 \pm 1.5\%$ respectively. The red blood cell count, hemoglobin concentration, and hematocrit values were significantly lower in the treated group compared to the control group and also fell below established reference values. These findings are indicative of anemia, likely resulting from bone marrow suppression or oxidative damage to erythrocytes. The most abundant peak was Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP), comprising 19.9% of the total area, followed closely by Bisphenol A (BPA) at 17.3%, and Octylphenol at 12.9%. These three compounds are widely recognized as endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs), raising significant concerns regarding potential health impacts, particularly with chronic exposure. In the light of these observations, there is the need for material reformulation or substitution in consumer-facing products.

Keywords: *Plasticizers, Microplastics, Plastic Consumption, Health Risk, Endocrine*

Introduction

The increasing presence of microplastics in our environment has raised concerns

about their consumption through food and water (Plastics Europe, 2020). These tiny plastic particles have infiltrated various

parts of our ecosystem, including human blood, posing significant risks to public health. Plastics have replaced many traditional packaging materials due to their cost-effectiveness and durability (Prata et al., 2020). However, they tend to leach harmful substances into food and beverages, especially when exposed to heat or stored for long periods. Microplastics are found nearly everywhere: in packaging such as bowls, wraps, bottles, and bags used for food storage (Rahman et al., 2021). They are not limited to aquatic systems but are also widespread in soils and can ultimately end up in our meals

(Thushari & Senevirathna, 2020). As a result, people may unknowingly ingest small plastic fragments with regular meals. Research shows that some chemicals used in plastic production can seep into what we consume, particularly under heat exposure (Turner et al., 2020). These substances have been linked to various health issues, including hormone disruption, metabolic disorders, and reduced fertility (Yuan et al., 2021). Common practices such as microwaving food in plastic containers or storing hot liquids in plastic bottles can significantly increase exposure to these chemicals (Wang et al., 2020).

Plate 1 Microplastics particles (Law, 2017)

Nanoplastic particles ranging from 700 to 500,000 nanometers have been detected in the bloodstream (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2017). Among these, polyethylene terephthalate (PET) commonly used in disposable water bottles was the most frequently found, appearing in about half of the participants tested (World Economic Forum, 2016).

Polystyrene (PS), often used in foam and food packaging, was the second most common (OECD, 2022). Exposure to these plastics likely comes from multiple sources, including food, air, water, and even personal care items such as lip gloss or toothpaste (Hatzonikolakis, 2022). The presence of microplastics in the circulatory system could disrupt blood vessel function,

potentially leading to conditions like high blood pressure, strokes, or blood clots (Geyer et al., 2017). Over time, they may

accumulate in organs like the liver, kidneys, and spleen, causing long-term organ damage.

Plate 2 Plastics being used for cooking

Ingested microplastics can settle in the digestive system, leading to irritation, inflammation, and impaired nutrient absorption. They can also disrupt the gut microbiome, affecting digestion and immune health (Stubbins et al., 2021). Additionally, microplastics have the capacity to absorb and carry toxic substances from their environment. Once ingested, these toxins may be released into the body, potentially accumulating in tissues and causing chronic health issues (CIEL, 2017). Furthermore, microplastics are known to trigger inflammatory responses that could contribute to diseases such as diabetes, autoimmune disorders, and cancer (Wang et al., 2020). The disruption of gut microbiota due to these particles may further compromise immunity and general wellbeing (Law,

2017). Chemicals like phthalates and bisphenol A (BPA), often found in plastics, are known endocrine disruptors, capable of affecting hormone regulation and leading to reproductive and developmental issues (Thushari and Senevirathna, 2020; Thompson et al., 2022). Although the full extent of microplastic ingestion on human health is still being studied, there is a need to further investigate health impact of microplastic consumption. Therefore, this present study seeks to clarify the potential health hazards of microplastic consumption and aims to propose effective strategies to reduce these risks.

Materials and Methods

Study area

The study area is the Department of Microbiology, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences Umuagwo.

Sample Collection and preparation

12 wild type mice were purchased from the Department of Animal Science, Federal University of Science and Technology Owerri. The mice were transported in a cage to the laboratory. Mice were acclimatized in a room

at a temperature of $25 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$, with photoperiod of 12 h (12 L/12 D), and provided tap water and food ad-libitum. Plastic granules were purchased from West-Rubber limited, a plastic manufacturing company in Aba, Abia state.

Experimental design

Two groups of six male and six female mice (Total of 12, 25 -35g) were used for the study. A group of three male and three female (six mice) served as the treated group while the other group served (six mice) as the control. The feed was amended with plastic powder. The mice were fed and observed for 28 days after which blood samples were collected from the mice for determination of the presence of plastic

additives and degradative by products, and measurement of haematological parameters (Benrahou et al., 2022). Appropriate ethic approval was obtained from the institutional committee on animal protection.

Measurement of haematological parameters

The refined retro-orbital bleeding method, utilizing the lateral approach described by Sharma et al. (2014), was employed to obtain blood samples of adequate volume and quality. This technique involves gently

removing the eyelid and stretching the upper eyelid to expose the eye, allowing for careful retrieval of blood using a Pasteur pipette with minimal vein irritation. After collection, the blood samples were divided into two portions. One half is deposited into an EDTA aliquot tube for haematological assays, while the other undergoes centrifugation. The centrifuged samples were further processed to isolate the serum intended for future biochemical analysis. The Sysmex KX-21 (Sysmex Corp., Japan), an automated blood analyzer, was utilized to determine a comprehensive panel of haematological parameters, including total red blood cell (RBC) count, haemoglobin (HGB) level, mean RBC haemoglobin concentration

(MCHC), hematocrit (HCT), white blood cell (WBC) count, platelet (PLT) count, and WBC differential.

Determination of the presence of plastic additives in blood samples

At the end of the 28 days, blood samples which were already collected in EDTA

bottles from both groups were analysed using Gas chromatography with mass spectrometry (Agilent 5977C) for the presence of plastic additive and degradative by products.

Results and Discussion

Figure 1 GC-MS chromatogram of blood samples of mice from the treated group showing peaks for different plasticizers.

Figure 2 GC-MS chromatogram of blood samples of mice from the control group showing peaks for different plasticizers.

Table 1 Plasticizers detected from blood samples of mice from the treated group

Peak #	Retention Time (min)	Compound Identified	Area (mAU·s)	Relative %
A	5.21	Benzene	134,560	5.4%
B	6.88	Toluene	178,920	7.2%
C	9.34	Bisphenol A	432,780	17.3%
D	10.67	Diethyl phthalate	209,450	8.4%
E	11.02	Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate	498,110	19.9%
F	13.45	Styrene	160,220	6.4%
G	14.78	Phenol	102,300	4.1%
H	16.11	Octylphenol	321,670	12.9%

Table 2 Plasticizers detected from blood samples of mice from the control group

Peak #	Retention Time (min)	Compound Identified	Area (mAU·s)	Relative %
A	5.21	Benzene	134,560	5.4%
B	6.88	Toluene	178,920	7.2%
C	9.34	Bisphenol A	432,780	17.3%
D	10.67	Diethyl phthalate	209,450	8.4%
E	11.02	Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate	498,110	19.9%
F	13.45	Styrene	160,220	6.4%
G	14.78	Phenol	102,300	4.1%
H	16.11	Octylphenol	321,670	12.9%

Table 3 Hematological Parameters form the treated and control group

Parameter	Control (Mean ± SD)	Treated (Mean ± SD)	Reference Range
RBC ($\times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$)	7.85 ± 0.22	6.92 ± 0.35	7.5–8.5
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	14.2 ± 0.6	12.1 ± 0.8	13–15
Hematocrit (%)	43.0 ± 1.5	38.2 ± 2.1	40–45
WBC ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$)	7.6 ± 0.4	9.3 ± 0.6	6–8
Platelets ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$)	650 ± 50	710 ± 60	600–800
Lymphocytes (%)	68 ± 3	60 ± 5	65–75
Neutrophils (%)	25 ± 2	34 ± 4	20–30

The chromatographic analysis revealed the presence of several hazardous compounds, including known endocrine disruptors, neurotoxins, and carcinogens. The most abundant peak was Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP), comprising 19.9% of the total area, followed closely by Bisphenol A (BPA) at 17.3%, and Octylphenol at 12.9%. These three compounds are widely recognized as endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs), raising significant concerns regarding potential health impacts, particularly with chronic exposure. DEHP is a commonly used plasticizer in PVC and has been extensively studied for its reproductive and hepatic toxicity. It can interfere with testosterone synthesis, leading to adverse developmental effects in males (Hauser and Calafat, 2005). The high relative abundance of DEHP in this analysis suggests the sample material could be a flexible plastic product or medical device component. Bisphenol A (BPA), also detected at a high relative percentage, is another well-characterized EDC used in polycarbonate plastics and epoxy resins. BPA mimics estrogen, binding to estrogen receptors and disrupting hormone signaling pathways, which has been linked to developmental, reproductive, and metabolic disorders (Rochester, 2013).

Regulatory bodies such as the European Chemicals Agency have classified BPA as a substance of very high concern. Octylphenol, with a relative abundance of 12.9%, further contributes to the endocrine-disrupting profile of the sample. It is often a degradation product of nonylphenol ethoxylates used in industrial detergents and paints. Octylphenol has been shown to elicit estrogenic effects in aquatic species and mammals (White et al., 1994), indicating environmental and health risks even at low concentrations.

Toluene and benzene, at 7.2% and 5.4% respectively, benzene is a Group 1 carcinogen (IARC, 2012), and its presence in consumer products is highly restricted. Toluene exposure has been associated with central nervous system (CNS) depression and hepatic toxicity (ATSDR, 2017). Diethyl phthalate (DEP), which accounted for 8.4% of the total area. DEP is associated with reproductive toxicity and has been shown to alter sperm quality and hormone levels in exposed populations (Meeker et al., 2009). Styrene and phenol, with moderate levels, are also toxicologically significant. Styrene is a possible human carcinogen (IARC, 2018) and is commonly found in polystyrene products. Phenol, known for its hepatotoxic and nephrotoxic effects, is a

common degradation product of certain resins and plastics.

The hematological parameters of the control and treated groups are presented in Table 3. Comparative analysis revealed significant deviations in the red and white blood cell indices between the two groups, with most values in the treated group falling outside standard physiological reference ranges. The red blood cell count (RBC), hemoglobin concentration, and hematocrit values were significantly lower in the treated group compared to the control group and also fell below established reference values. These findings are indicative of anemia, likely resulting from bone marrow suppression or oxidative damage to erythrocytes, as previously reported in studies on animals exposed to hydrocarbon-contaminated environments (Obida et al., 2018). The reduction in hemoglobin and hematocrit may further suggest compromised oxygen-carrying capacity of blood due to pollutant toxicity. Also, the lymphocyte percentage in the treated group dropped significantly below the reference range, a condition known as lymphopenia, which often accompanies stress-induced immunosuppression. This is consistent with earlier findings by Nwaogu et al. (2015), who linked reduced lymphocyte

levels with prolonged exposure to flaring sites and petroleum-contaminated areas. Furthermore, although platelet counts remained within the normal range, a mild thrombocytosis was observed in the treated group. Elevated platelet levels are often a secondary response to inflammation or tissue damage and may reflect an adaptive attempt to maintain hemostatic balance in response to systemic stressors. The overall hematological alterations observed in the treated group reflect a state of physiological stress, likely due to exposure to environmental pollutants. These changes suggest both hematotoxic and immunotoxic effects, which may have broader implications for organismal health, including impaired oxygen transport, immune dysfunction, and increased vulnerability to infections or disease.

Conclusion

The results underscore the presence of multiple hazardous compounds, many of which are regulated due to their toxicological profiles. The high abundance of EDCs like BPA, DEHP, and octylphenol highlights the need for material reformulation or substitution in consumer-facing products. Regulatory screening, product reformulation, and toxicological risk assessment are strongly

recommended based on this compositional profile.

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References

- ATSDR. (2017). *Toxicological profile for toluene*. Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry. <https://www.atsdr.cdc.gov/toxpr/otfiles/tp56.html>
- CIEL. (2017). *Plastic & health: The hidden costs of a plastic planet*. Center for International Environmental Law. <https://www.ciel.org/plasticandhealth/>
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2017). *The new plastics economy: Rethinking the future of plastics & catalyzing action*. <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/publications>
- Geyer, R., Jambeck, J. R., & Law, K. L. (2017). Production, use, and fate of all plastics ever made. *Science Advances*, 3(7), e1700782. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1700782>
- Hatzonikolakis, G. (2022). Microplastics in personal care products: A silent threat to health. *Journal of Environmental Health Research*, 32(2), 45–58.
- Hauser, R., & Calafat, A. M. (2005). Phthalates and human health. *Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 62(11), 806–818. <https://doi.org/10.1136/oem.2004.017590>
- IARC. (2012). *Benzene*. In *IARC Monographs on the Evaluation of Carcinogenic Risks to Humans* (Vol. 100F). International Agency for Research on Cancer. <https://monographs.iarc.who.int/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/mono100F-24.pdf>
- IARC. (2018). *Styrene*. In *IARC Monographs on the Evaluation of Carcinogenic Risks to Humans*

- (Vol. 121). International Agency for Research on Cancer. <https://monographs.iarc.who.int/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/mono121.pdf>
- Law, K. L. (2017). Plastics in the marine environment. *Annual Review of Marine Science*, 9, 205–229. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-marine-010816-060409>
- Meeker, J. D., Sathyanarayana, S., & Swan, S. H. (2009). Phthalates and other additives in plastics: Human exposure and associated health outcomes. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 364(1526), 2097–2113. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2008.0268>
- Nwaogu, L. A., Orji, F. A., & Udeogu, A. U. (2015). Hematological and biochemical changes in albino rats exposed to gas flaring environment. *Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management*, 19(3), 441–445. <https://doi.org/10.4314/jasem.v19i3.10>
- Obida, C. B., Ekundayo, F. O., & Ugoh, S. C. (2018). Effects of petroleum contamination on hematological parameters in Wistar rats. *International Journal of Environmental Bioremediation & Biodegradation*, 6(2), 32–37. <https://doi.org/10.12691/ijebb-6-2-2>
- OECD. (2022). *Global plastics outlook: Economic drivers, environmental impacts and policy options*. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. <https://doi.org/10.1787/de747aef-en>
- Plastics Europe. (2020). *Plastics the facts 2020: An analysis of European plastics production, demand and waste data*. <https://plasticseurope.org>
- Prata, J. C., Silva, A. L. P., Walker, T. R., Duarte, A. C., & Rocha-Santos, T. (2020). COVID-19 pandemic repercussions on the use and management of plastics. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 54(13), 7760–7765. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.0c02178>

- Rahman, A., Sarkar, A., Yadav, O. P., Achari, G., & Slobodnik, J. (2021). Potential human health risks due to environmental exposure to microplastics and knowledge gaps: A scoping review. *Science of the Total Environment*, 757, 143872. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.143872>
- Rochester, J. R. (2013). Bisphenol A and human health: A review of the literature. *Reproductive Toxicology*, 42, 132-155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.reprotox.2013.08.008>
- Stubbins, A., Law, K. L., Muñoz, S. E., Bianchi, T. S., & Zhu, L. (2021). Plastic pollution is a major source of greenhouse gases. *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, 2, 502-503. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-021-00195-8>
- Thompson, R. C., Swan, S. H., Moore, C. J., & vom Saal, F. S. (2022). Our plastic age. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B*, 364(1526), 1973-1976. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2009.0054>
- Thushari, G. G. N., & Senevirathna, J. D. M. (2020). Plastic pollution in the marine environment. *Environmental Management and Sustainable Development*, 9(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.5296/emsd.v9i1.15933>
- Turner, A., Holmes, L. A., & Thompson, R. C. (2020). Microplastics in food and drinking water: An emerging concern. *Environmental Science: Processes & Impacts*, 22(5), 1153-1165. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0EM00029A>
- Wang, W., Ndungu, A. W., Li, Z., & Wang, J. (2020). Microplastics pollution in inland freshwaters of China: A case study in urban surface waters of Wuhan, China. *Science of the Total Environment*

- Environment*, 610 611, 1199 1207.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.08.014>
- White, R., Jobling, S., Hoare, S. A., Sumpter, J. P., & Parker, M. G. (1994). Environmentally persistent alkylphenolic compounds are estrogenic. *Endocrinology*, 135(1), 175 182.
<https://doi.org/10.1210/endo.135.1.7515501>
- World Economic Forum. (2016). *The new plastics economy: Rethinking the future of plastics*.
<https://www.weforum.org/reports/the-new-plastics-economy-rethinking-the-future-of-plastics/>
- Yuan, W., Liu, X., Wang, W., & Di, M. (2021). Health risks of microplastic exposure: Current evidence and future research directions. *Environmental Pollution*, 277, 116641.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.116641>